

- Lysinibacillus
- Bacillus
- Robinsoniella
- Roseburia
- unclassified_Lachnospiraceae
- Sporacetigenium
- Clostridium
- Sporobacter
- Subdoligranulum
- unclassified_Ruminococcaceae
- Acetivibrio
- Oscillibacter
- unclassified_Clostridiales
- unclassified_Clostridia

- unclassified_Firmicutes
- Campylobacter
- Akkermansia
- unclassified_Bacteria
- Bacteroides
- Barnesiella
- unclassified_Porphyrmonadaceae
- Parabacteroides
- Alistipes
- unclassified_Rikenellaceae
- unclassified_Bacteroidales
- unclassified_Bacteroidetes
- Escherichia.Shigella
- Other_bacteria